

Studies in Dieckmann Cyclisation. Part I. Cyclisation of Triethyl 2-Methylpentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate

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The Dieckmann cyclisation of triethyl 2-methylpentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate under widely different conditions lead to the formation of a five-ring rather than six-ring product. A postulate involving the steric interaction in the transition state intermediate for six-ring product has been proposed to explain this difference. The cyclisation involving relatively improbable anion (cf. Woodward and Eastman, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 68, 2232) has not been observed. Operation of steric retardation in the retrogression of the Dieckmann cyclisation has been demonstrated by the action of OEt^- on (IVb).

The Dieckmann cyclisation of triethyl 2-methylpentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate (I) using sodium dust in anhydrous benzene was first investigated by Banerjee, (this *Journal*, 1940, 17, 423). The structure of the resulting β -keto-ester (II) was established by isolation of 1-methyl-2-oxo-cyclopentylacetic acid (III) from the hydrolysis product (Chakravarti and Banerjee, *Ibid.*, 1946, 23, 387). These authors were able to isolate only one keto-acid (III) from the hydrolysis product and none of the isomeric six-ring keto-acid (V), which would have been formed if the intermediate β -keto-ester had either of the alternative structures (IVa) or (IVb). These authors offered no explanation for the preferential formation of (II) rather than (IVa) or (IVb).

Chakravarti (*Experientia*, 1947, 3, 149) proposed a possible explanation for the preferential formation of the five-membered cyclisation product (II) and attributed it solely to

the diminished ionisation at C₁ due to the positive character (electron releasing) of the methyl group. It is, however, difficult to explain the absence of (IVb) only on the above ground. Hammond and Hogle (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 338) have concluded that the accumulation of bulky substituents adjacent to the carboxyl group of fatty acids has a pronounced acid-weakening effect on the carboxylic acids. These data *cannot* be related to the *electronic influences* of the various alkyl groups. Hammond (M. S. Newmann, *Steric Effects in Organic Chemistry*, John Wiley & Sons, 1956, 426) pointed out that steric effects in ionisation reactions of carboxylic acids are highly complicated and are combination of (a) steric inhibition of resonance, (b) the exclusion of solvents from the vicinity of the functional group in the charged form involved in the equilibrium and (c) special interactions such as hydrogen bonding etc. The same generalisations might be expected to hold good for the ionisation of the pseudo-acids of the ester type which are involved in the Dieckmann cyclisation. Moreover, Reed and Thornely (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2148) have adduced evidence for the existence of steric retardation in the Dieckmann cyclisation of adipic esters due to the presence of alkyl groups.

The above considerations led us to reinvestigate cyclisation of triethyl 2-methylpentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate (I), particularly with a view to ascertaining a suitable condition for obtaining the six-ring product (IVa) or (IVb) through alternative cyclisation. Banerjee *et al.* (*Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1957, 48, 80) demonstrated that the lower homologue triethylpentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate (I; Me=H) could be cyclised to a five-ring product (II; Me=H) in ethanol in presence of molecular quantity of sodium ethoxide, whereas the alternative cyclisation to six-ring product (IVa; Me=H) was known to proceed by the action of sodium dust in benzene (Johnson *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 2010). Banerjee *et al.* (*loc. cit.*) concluded that the direction of cyclisation of the above triester was dependent on the concentration of the ethoxyl ion. These findings could be rationalised if one considered that, as the cyclisation product was thrown out of the reaction medium as insoluble salt, the cyclisation in benzene medium was probably a kinetically controlled process and the cyclisation in ethanolic medium was thermodynamically controlled, the thermodynamically more stable five-ring product being formed.

In the present investigation when the cyclisation was carried out according to the procedure of Banerjee *et al.* (*loc. cit.*), the resulting β -keto-ester on hydrolysis yielded mainly 1-methyl-2-oxo-cyclopentylacetic acid as in the cyclisation in benzene solution (Banerjee, *loc. cit.*). This was further characterised as 2,4-D.N.P.H. derivative and the latter showed no depression when mixed with 2, 4-D.N.P.H. of an authentic sample of 1-methyl-2-oxo-cyclopentylacetic acid, but showed considerable depression on admixture with an authentic sample of the D.N.P.H. of 1-methyl-2-oxo-cyclohexanecarboxylic acid (V).

An attempt to resolve the D. N. P. H. of the crude keto acid furnished by the hydrolysis of the cyclisation product of the triester (I), obtained according to the procedure of Banerjee (*loc. cit.*), into more than one product using paper chromatographic method proved abortive.

According to Bell (*Ann. Rep. London*, 1939, 82) the velocity of a reaction could be raised by a factor of about 10^3 by a change of solvent, there being a general tendency for higher rates in solvents of a polar type. It was therefore considered that the velocity of reactions of the different carboxyl groups at C₁ and C₂ in the triester (I) with the anion of the methylene group (*vide infra*) might be affected to a different degree in different solvents so that alternative cyclisation product might be obtained by the change of solvent.

With the above end in view the cyclisation of triethyl 2-methylpentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate was further investigated using sodium methoxide in methanol, potassium butoxide⁴ in butanol¹ and sodium dust in xylene. The cyclisation product in each case was hydrolysed to the keto-acid and the latter characterised through the semicarbazone and D. N. P. H. derivatives. The keto-acid in each of the above cases was found to be 1-methyl-2-oxo-cyclopentylacetic acid by a comparison of the m.p. and the mixed m.p. with an authentic sample and its derivatives.

The authentic sample of 1-methyl-2-oxo-cyclopentylacetic acid (III) was prepared by a new method following the procedure of Birch *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1390, 1994; 1945, 582). This method is superior to those recorded in the literature (Chakravarti and Banerjee, *loc. cit.*; Buchta *et al.*, *Chem. Ber.*, 1958, 91, 1552; see also references cited therein). The methylanilinomethylene derivative (VIA) of methyl cyclopentanone-2-acetate was methylated with potassium butoxide⁴ and methyl iodide. The methylated product (VIB) on hydrolysis furnished the authentic keto-acid (III, m.p. 68-69°), yielding a semicarbazone (m.p. 203-204°) and 2, 4-D.N.P.H. derivative m.p. 148-49°; D.N.P.H. of methyl ester, m.p. 132-32.5°, $\lambda_{\max}$ (CHCl₃) 361 m μ (ϵ 26,900).

An authentic sample of 1-methyl-3-oxo cyclohexane-carboxylic acid (V) was prepared for comparison by hydrolysis of the corresponding methyl ester (V:R''=Me), obtained according to the method of Whitmore and Roberts (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1948, 13, 31). The acid, obtained crystalline for the first time, melted at 78-79°; it was characterised through a semicarbazone, m.p. 190° (decomp) and 2,-D.N.P.H. derivative, m.p. 155-56°; D.N.P.H. of the methyl ester, m.p. 129.5°, $\lambda_{\max}$ (CHCl₃) 366 m μ (ϵ 26,200).

(VIA : R=H. VIB : R=Me)

The experimental results outlined above strongly indicate the reluctance of the triester (I) to yield a six-membered product (IVa) or (IVb). Considering the electronic effects in operation the carboxyl group at C₁ appears to be more reactive than the one attached to C₂ due to the electron-releasing effect of the methyl group (Reed and Thornley, *loc. cit.*). Moreover, the former is considerably less crowded than the latter. The cyclisation involving the carboxyl at C₁ to give (IVb) thus appears to be more facile. The true picture, however, could be obtained through the analysis of the steric effects operating at the transition state.

In accordance with the accepted mechanism (Ingold, "Structure and Mechanism in Organic Chemistry", Cornell University Press, New York, 1953, 793; Reed and Thornley, *loc. cit.*) the cyclisation of the triethyl ester might be considered to proceed in the following stages (A-D):

The initial step A is a proton-transfer reaction and it might be expected that a pronounced acid-weakening effect due to the accumulation of bulky substituents (Hammond and Hogle, *loc. cit.*) should reduce the ionisation of the proton at C_1 . Consequently, the anion formation should be predominant at C_5 . The step B involves the addition of the mesomeric anion to the carbonyl group probably through the transition state formed by the overlap of the π -orbital of the mesomeric anion with the electrophilic centre of the carbonyl group.

In the above sequence the importance of the final step D is to keep the concentration of the keto-form produced at the stage C at a low equilibrium value and thus to promote the reaction in right direction.

The transition state intermediate corresponding to a six-ring compound at the stage B should be represented by (IIc) or (IId).

(IIc : $R=O^-$; $R'=OEt$)

(IIId : $R=OEt$; $R'=O^-$)

The formation of such intermediates (IIc) and (IIId) involves considerably higher energy than (IIb) since the former involve 1:3-diaxial interaction between $^-O:CH_3$ and $OC_2H_5:CH_3$. On the evidence of Catalin models, the eclipse interactions in the five-ring transition state (IIb) appear to be much less than the 1:3-diaxial interactions in the six-ring transition states (IIc and IIId). It should be pointed out that these structures represent extreme forms, the actual transition state intermediates being probably more flexible. These considerations require the postulation of the fundamental nature of the steric interactions in the transition state intermediate in the Dieckmann cyclisation in addition to electronic effects.

The formation of a relatively improbable anion was ruled out (cf. Woodward and Eastman, *loc. cit.*) since the cyclisation of the triester (I) in xylene solution, followed by hydrolysis of the product, furnished the same 1-methyl-2-oxo-cyclopentylacetic acid.

Finally, the action of sodium ethoxide in ethanol on diethyl 4-methyl-2-ketocyclohexane-1, 4-dicarboxylate (IVb) (Dutta & Biswas, Part II, this *Journal*, in press) did not bring about the transformation into (II) (cf. Banerjee *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) indicating the operation of steric retardation in the addition of ^-OEt to the carbonyl group of (IVb) prior to the reversal of the Dieckmann cyclisation to form (IIc).

EXPERIMENTAL*

Dieckmann Cyclisation of Triethyl 2-Methylpentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate (I) with Sodium Ethoxide in Ethanol Solution.—A mixture of the triester (I, 5.06 g.) and sodium ethoxide (0.8 g. of Na in 20 c.c. of magnesium ethoxide-dried ethanol) in ethanol was heated under reflux (bath temperature 100°) for $3\frac{1}{2}$ hours. The reaction mixture was cooled, acidified with ice-cold HCl (dil.), diluted with ice water and extracted with ether. The solvent was removed and the residue, which gave violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride, was heated under reflux with a mixture of 20% HCl (28 c.c.) and glacial acetic acid (14 c.c.) during 30 hours. The solvents were removed under reduced pressure at $130-40^\circ$ and the residue was evaporatively distilled at $105-110^\circ$ (0.4 mm). The distillate (1.9 g., 73%) solidified on standing and was crystallised from ether-petroleum ether (40-60°) mixture; after drying in vacuum

*All m.p.'s are corrected; the absorption spectra were taken in chloroform solution using a Hilger spectrophotometer.

(0.4 mm) at room temperature a white crystalline product (850 mg.), m.p. 68-69°, was obtained. On admixture with an authentic specimen of same m.p. there was no depression. The semicarbazone prepared by the sodium acetate method after crystallisation from water melted at 202-203° and did not depress the m.p. of an authentic sample. The 2,4-D.N.P.H. derivative, prepared by the perchloric acid method (Neuberg *et al.*, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1952, 7, 238) was crystallised from EtAc-MeOH mixture, m.p. 148-49°, undepressed on admixture with an authentic sample. The 2,4-D.N.P.H. derivative of the methyl ester prepared by diazomethane method[†] was crystallised from EtAc-MeOH, m.p. 132-32.5°.

With Sodium Methoxide in Methanol.—A mixture of the tri-ester (I, 5.0 g.) and sodium methoxide solution (from 0.8 g. of sodium and 20 c.c. of anhydrous methanol) was heated under reflux (oil bath 85-90°) for 4 hours. Proceeding in the same way as above the keto-acid (0.8 g., 30%) was obtained. The distillate on crystallisation furnished a white crystalline solid (120 mg.), m.p. 68-69°; semicarbazone m.p. 202-203°, D.N.P.H. m.p. 148-149°. It was identified as 1-methyl-2-oxo-cyclopentylacetic acid by mixed m.p. determination. D.N.P.H. of the methyl ester m.p. 132-32.5°.

With Potassium Butoxide in Butanol.—To a solution of potassium (0.99 g.) in butanol[†] (25 c.c.) triester (I, 5.06 g.) was added and the mixture heated under reflux for 6 hours on an oil bath (100-105°). The reaction mixture was cooled and excess the solvent removed under reduced pressure. On working up as above a viscous liquid distillate (1.5 g., 61%) was obtained which on crystallisation furnished the same keto-acid (III) as a crystalline solid m.p. 68-69°, semicarbazone m.p. 202-203°, D.N.P.H. m.p. 148-49°. D.N.P.H. of the methyl ester, m.p. 132-32.5°.

With Sodium Dust in Xylene solution.—To a suspension of powdered sodium (0.76 g.) in xylene (20 c.c.) the triester (I, 5.06 g.) was added and the mixture was heated to boiling till all the sodium had dissolved (1.5 hrs.). On working up in the usual manner the keto-acid (1.3 g., 50%) m.p. 68-69° was obtained. It was identified as 1-methyl-2-oxo-cyclopentyl acetic acid through the comparison of the semicarbazone, m.p. 202-203° and D.N.P.H. derivative m.p. 148-149°, with those of the authentic sample. D.N.P.H. of the methyl ester, m.p. 132-32.5°.

A New Procedure for the Authentic Sample of 1-Methyl-2-oxo-cyclopentylacetic Acid (III)

To a suspension of sodium methoxide (from 0.98 g. of sodium and 1.6 c.c. anhydrous methanol) in dry thiophene-free benzene (15 c.c.), cooled in freezing mixture and kept in an atmosphere of nitrogen, was added dropwise a solution of ethyl formate (5.7 c.c.) and methyl cyclopentanone-2-acetate (3.1 g.) in dry thiophene-free benzene (10 c.c.) with continuous shaking. After 15 minutes the solution became deep brown and it was kept in the ice bath for 2 hours with occasional shaking. After leaving at room temperature for 48 hours iced water was added to the reaction mixture and the benzene layer was separated. The benzene layer was washed with ice-cold dilute solution of KOH (2%; 3 × 20 c.c.) and the alkaline extracts were added to the aqueous layer. The combined aqueous and alkaline extract was washed with ether and acidified with ice-cold 6*N* HCl. The organic material was taken up in ether, washed with water, and dried (Na₂SO₄). On removal of ether by distillation and the volatile material in high vacuum the residual formyl derivative of methyl cyclopentanone-2-acetate weighed 2.76 g. It gave characteristic violet coloration with ethanolic ferric chloride.

To the cooled solution of the above crude hydroxymethylene derivative (2.76 g.) in dry thiophene-free benzene (15 c.c.) was added dropwise freshly distilled monomethylaniline (3.3 c.c.). The mixture was swirled for some time and then left at room temperature for 24 hours. Benzene was slowly distilled from water bath. Additional benzene (30 c.c.) was added and removed by slow distillation; this operation was repeated thrice. The residue was evacuated under high vacuum at 70-80° for 1 hour and then for 2 hours at room temperature in order to remove monomethylaniline (excess) and other volatile products. The residue consisted mainly of the methylanilinomethylene derivative (VIA) of methyl cyclopentanone-2-acetate and weighed 4.09 g.

To a stirred solution of potassium butoxide[†] [from potassium (2.4g.) and dry butanol[†] (60 c.c.)] in a three-necked flask, cooled in an ice bath, was added dropwise the solution of the crude methylanilinomethylene derivative in dry thiophene-free benzene during which the whole system was kept in nitrogen atmosphere. After continuing the stirring for about 1½ hours methyl iodide (11.1 c.c.) was added and the reaction mixture was stirred for a further period of 4 hours at room temperature. The major part of the solvent was removed on water bath under water suction. The residual yellowish product was treated with ice-cold water (100 c.c.) containing HCl (conc., 3 c.c.). The product was taken up in benzene-ether mixture and the aqueous layer twice extracted with ether. The combined extract was thoroughly washed with water, dried (Na₂SO₄), and the solvents were removed. The brown residue (2.5 g.) thus obtained was directly utilised in the next operation.

The above crude methylated product (2.5 g.) was heated under reflux with 10% HCl (100 c.c.) in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 1½ hours. The reaction mixture was cooled and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution was washed with brine and the solvent was removed. The residue (violet coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride) was heated under reflux with aqueous 10% KOH solution (50 c.c.) in an atmosphere of nitrogen for 2 hours. The cooled reaction product was acidified with ice-cold HCl (dil.) and extracted with ether. The extract after drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate was freed from the solvent on a water bath. The residue, which gave no coloration with alcoholic ferric chloride, was evaporatively distilled at 120-30°/11 mm. The distillate (450 mg.) on crystallisation from ether-petroleum ether (40-60°) mixture furnished a white crystalline solid, m.p. 68-69°. (Found: C, 61.43; H, 7.78. C₈H₁₂O₃ requires C, 61.53; H, 7.69%).

The semicarbazone of the keto-acid was prepared by the sodium acetate method and recrystallised from water, m.p. 202-203°.

The 2,4-D.N.P.H. of the methyl ester of the keto-acid (prepared by diazomethane method) on crystallisation from EtAc-MeOH melted at 132-32.5°, λ_{max} (CHCl₃), 361 mμ (ε 26,900).

1-Methyl-3-oxo-cyclohexanecarboxylic acid (V).

Methyl 1-methyl-3-oxo-cyclohexanecarboxylate (2.0 g.) was heated under reflux with 20% HCl (20 c.c.) for 60 hours. After cooling, the solution was saturated with ammonium sulphate and extracted twice with ether. The combined ethereal extract was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent removed. The residue was evaporatively distilled at 110-15° (0.2 mm). The distillate solidified on cooling and was crystallised from ether-petroleum ether (40-60°). The crystalline solid thus obtained melted at 78-79°. (Found: C, 61.49; H, 7.82. C₈H₁₂O₃ requires C, 61.53; H, 7.69%).

The semicarbazone was prepared by the sodium acetate method and recrystallised from water, m.p. 190° (decomp.). The 2,4-D.N.P.H. derivative was prepared by the

perchloric acid method (Neuberg *et al.*, *loc. cit.*) and on crystallisation from EtAc-MeOH melted at 155-56°.

The D. N. P. H. derivative of the methyl ester of the keto-acid melted at 129.5°. λ_{max} (CHCl₃) 366 m μ (ϵ 26,200).

Action of Sodium Ethoxide on Diethyl 4-Methyl 2-oxo-cyclohexane-1, 4-dicarboxylate (IVb).

To a solution of sodium (0.25 g.) in anhydrous ethanol (distilled over magnesium ethoxide, 4.5 c.c.) the keto-diester (IVb) (prepared according to procedure described in Part II) (2.4 g.) was added and the solution was heated under reflux for 7½ hours in an oil bath. After cooling the reaction mixture was acidified with ice-cold H₂SO₄ (dil.) and extracted twice with ether. The combined ethereal extract was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removal of the solvent the residue (violet colour with alcoholic ferric chloride) was heated under reflux with a mixture of 20% HCl (14 c.c.) and glacial acetic acid (7 c.c.) for 20 hours. The volatile material was removed under water suction on an oil bath at 130-40°. After removal of the traces of moisture by azeotropic distillation with benzene, the residue was evaporatively distilled at 110-15° (0.5 mm). The distillate (0.8 g.) solidified on cooling. On crystallisation from ether-petroleum ether (40-60°) mixture it furnished a solid, m.p. 78-79°, which showed no depression on admixture with an authentic sample of 1-methyl-3-oxo-cyclohexanecarboxylic acid. The semicarbazone, m.p. 190° (decomp.) and the 2,4-D.N.P.H. derivative m.p. 155-156° did not depress the m.p. of the corresponding derivatives of the authentic sample.

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